

**OUR 7TH NEWSLETTER
IS HERE!**

Dear friends, partners and colleagues,

Welcome to the **7th edition of the e-SAFE newsletter**, covering key developments from **December 2023 to today**. During the past year, our **pilot projects in Catania, Timisoara, and Bucharest** have seen important milestones. In Catania, e-SAFE was featured in the regional press, highlighting the urgency of seismic and energy retrofiting. In Timisoara, we successfully completed the co-design phase, setting the groundwork for implementation, while in Bucharest, residents actively engaged in the co-design process and discussions on renovation solutions tailored to their needs, and funding has been secured to transform the plans into reality for the community.

Beyond our pilot sites, we have been **expanding knowledge-sharing efforts**. The launch of the **e-SAFE training program (e-TRAINING)** has provided key stakeholders—engineers, architects, and policymakers—with the tools to apply integrated renovation solutions.

It's an important moment for renovation **policy in this key year for EPBD transposition**, and project partners are encouraged to double down on efforts to ensure that national authorities are aware of how to implement the Energy Performance of Buildings Directive (EPBD) in a way that promotes both energy efficiency and seismic safety.

With **2025 shaping up to be a crucial year for EU policies on building renovation**, e-SAFE remains committed to bridging the gap between innovation and real-world application. We invite you to explore the latest updates in this issue and join us in shaping a safer, more sustainable built environment.

Happy reading!

Sunny regards from Catania,

Giuseppe Margani & the e-SAFE team

Transposing the EPBD: ensuring safe, efficient and resilient buildings

2025 will be a pivotal year as the European Commission publishes key initiatives and launches strategic documents that will shape the new mandate, which officially started on 1 December 2024.

For **deep renovations and building decarbonisation**, it will be crucial to bring learnings from the ground and projects such as e-SAFE to influence **concrete policy proposals**, including both regulations and funding mechanisms. Notably, the new Multiannual Financial Framework (MFF) for the period 2028-2034 is expected to be proposed around summer 2025.

The context is challenging. Topics like competitiveness and a focus on specific technologies are prominent in the EU discourse, potentially posing risks to climate ambitions and emissions reduction efforts in the building sector.

The **Energy Performance of Buildings Directive (EPBD)**, adopted in 2024, must be transposed by the end of May 2026. It remains essential to emphasise the importance of EPBD implementation for seismic strengthening and reducing emissions in buildings, alongside its broader benefits.

ENSURING SAFE AND ENERGY EFFICIENT BUILDINGS

How to integrate seismic-safety with energy renovations in the EPBD

Read the policy paper [here](#)

Further efforts are needed to clarify the Directive provisions and guide national authorities and agencies tasked with implementation. **e-SAFE project partners are called upon to continue dissemination efforts and ensure that national-level actors are aware of the key EPBD provisions for enabling an integrated approach to renovation**, such as outlined in the first [e-SAFE policy paper](#).

Other upcoming European Commission initiatives, including the **Affordable Housing Plan**, present significant opportunities to enhance the state of buildings across Europe. An own-initiative report from the European Parliament is expected by the end of 2025, and a Commission proposal in early 2026.

The last word: energy security has re-emerged as a central topic, closely related to efforts to end Russian energy imports. This development presents **an opportunity to highlight the strategic importance of resilient and decarbonised buildings for Europe's energy system**, sovereignty, and independence.

Updates from the e-SAFE pilots

Stay up-to-date on
the pilots

CATANIA

The screenshot shows the top of a La Sicilia news article. At the top, there are navigation links for various Sicilian cities: Catania, Agrigento, Caltanissetta, Enna, Messina, and Palermo. Below this is a Google AdSense banner with the text 'Annunci Google' and a 'Nascondi annuncio' button. The article title is 'A Catania l'80% degli edifici sono stati realizzati prima della normativa antisismica'. Below the title is a sub-headline: 'E il 90% è nato prima delle norme sul consumo energetico. Problemi affrontati dal progetto e-SAFE dell'Università di Catania, di cui il 29 novembre si presentano i risultati'. The article is dated '28 Novembre 2024'. Below the text is a photograph of a multi-story building under renovation, with scaffolding and construction materials visible. A purple callout bubble with a mouse cursor icon points to the text 'Read the full article here (in Italian)'.

e-SAFE featured in La Sicilia

A recent article in La Sicilia highlighted the structural challenges of Catania's building stock, noting that around 80% of buildings were constructed before modern seismic regulations. This underlines the need for retrofitting solutions that improve both safety and energy efficiency. The article also covered our two-day consortium meeting of all e-SAFE project partners at the University of Catania, where we presented the project's findings and discussed future applications. This recognition helps bring attention to the importance of integrated retrofitting strategies in regions like Catania.

8th consortium meeting

During the last week of November 2024, the e-SAFE consortium gathered in Catania for its 8th project meeting, bringing together partners from across Europe to review progress and plan the next steps. A key highlight was the significant advancements in the pilot project, in Via Acquicella Porto, Catania.

Another important topic was the e-SAFE training program, designed to equip professionals with the knowledge and tools needed to apply these innovative solutions effectively. This initiative will support engineers, architects, and policymakers in implementing best practices for safer and more energy-efficient buildings.

As the project moves forward, the focus remains on finalizing technical developments, sharing insights from the pilot, and ensuring the broader adoption of e-SAFE solutions.

Read more about the meeting

e-Training kicks off

On 29 January 2025, e-SAFE project hosted its **first e-TRAINING event in Catania**. This training marked an important step in ensuring that engineers, architects, and policymakers have the necessary knowledge and skills to implement e-SAFE solutions in real-world applications.

The event covered key aspects of the project's integrated approach, providing participants with practical insights into new technologies and methodologies for improving building resilience and energy efficiency. This successful session was the first in a series of face-to-face training events in four different countries.

The second e-TRAINING took place in February in Bologna, while the next ones will be in April in Athens, in Amsterdam in May and in Timisoara in June.

Discover the outcomes

TIMISOARA

Co-design complete: fundraising efforts ongoing

A major milestone was reached with the completion of the co-design process for the Timisoara pilot project. This participatory approach ensured that technical solutions were developed in alignment with local needs and expectations. The pilot will serve as a demonstration of e-SAFE's integrated retrofitting solutions, providing a model for future renovations in earthquake-prone areas.

Currently, the main challenge for the platform is securing the necessary funding to implement the outputs of the co-design process. Efforts are underway to raise the funds required to bring these solutions to life and demonstrate their real-world impact. Stay tuned for updates via the [Timisoara Local Platform](#) – and don't forget the BPIE e-training event which will be taking place in June 2025 in Timisoara.

Check out the playlist from the Timisoara pilot

We invite you to explore this YouTube playlist, with a set of videos following key developments in the Timisoara pilot. The playlist also features a TV interview with project partners, providing valuable insights into the importance of seismic and energy retrofitting and the challenges faced in earthquake-prone regions. Through expert discussions, field updates, and behind-the-scenes footage, these videos offer a comprehensive view of the project's approach to making buildings safer and more efficient.

BUCHAREST

Residents embrace e-SAFE renovation solutions

On 12 March 2024, e-SAFE partners UNICT and BPIE met with AMCCRS and residents to discuss innovative building renovation solutions. The meeting presented various options, from basic seismic upgrades to more advanced solutions that include private outdoor spaces like balconies, improving both safety and comfort.

Residents were enthusiastic about enhancing their living spaces and asked detailed questions about the renovation process. Both AMCCRS and the residents expressed positive feedback, recognizing the innovation behind e-SAFE's approach. This meeting marks the first step in implementing the renovation plan for which funding has been secured. Read more [here](#).

A new educational initiative: e-SAFE Academy webinar series

The e-SAFE Academy's educational series began with its first successful webinar on **Transforming Deep Renovation in Buildings Across Europe: e-SAFE Business Models and Financial Schemes**. The event explored innovative business models and financial mechanisms that support deep renovation in Europe.

The second webinar followed up with a focus on **Envelope Solutions for Seismic and Energy Renovation**, addressing the integration of seismic and energy efficiency in building envelopes.

Both webinar recordings will be available soon on the [e-SAFE YouTube channel](#).

The third webinar, scheduled for 8 May 2025, will dive into **e-THERM: An Efficient Solution for Renovating Thermal Systems**.

More details will be out soon, but you can already save your spot!

The graphic features a purple and green color scheme. On the left, the e-SAFE logo is shown above the text 'e-SAFE Academy Webinar'. Below this, the main title 'e-THERM: an efficient solution for renovating the thermal systems' is displayed in white. A white callout box on the right contains the date and time: '8th May 2025, 14 CET, online on Zoom'. A circular inset image shows solar panels on a rooftop. At the bottom left, a white button with a mouse cursor icon says 'Register here!'. A small text box at the bottom left of the graphic reads: 'The e-THERM has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 693335.'

e-SAFE Academy Webinar

e-THERM: an efficient solution for renovating the thermal systems

8th May 2025
14 CET
online on Zoom

Register here!

The e-THERM has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 693335.

Out and about: Showcasing innovation and collaboration

The e-SAFE project continues to make waves at key events across Europe, highlighting its innovative approach to seismic and energy-efficient building renovations. Recently, e-SAFE was featured in several important industry gatherings, showcasing the project's contributions to sustainable building practices.

Green Deal Greece 2024

At the Green Deal Greece 2024 conference, e-SAFE was proud to showcase its innovative concepts for building renovation. The event provided a platform for sharing affordable and practical solutions for improving building resilience and energy efficiency. e-SAFE's participation emphasized the importance of integrated approaches to tackling seismic vulnerability and energy inefficiency in the European built environment.

Kick-off meeting for the Network of Building Renovation Projects

e-SAFE also joined the kick-off meeting for the Network of Building Renovation Projects, a collaborative initiative focused on fostering knowledge exchange and cooperation in the field of building renovation.

This platform allows e-SAFE to engage with other projects and stakeholders, strengthening its efforts in promoting best practices and scalable solutions for energy-efficient and seismically safe buildings.

OpenLivingLab Days 2024 in Timisoara

e-SAFE made a significant impact at the OpenLivingLab Days 2024 in Timisoara, where Dr. Ioan Silviu Dobosi presented the project's progress. The event brought together innovators, researchers, and industry professionals to discuss energy transition strategies. e-SAFE's solutions for retrofitting buildings with a focus on energy efficiency and seismic safety were key highlights, drawing interest from attendees that are keen to implement similar strategies in their own regions.

These events reflect e-SAFE's growing presence in the building renovation sector, bringing together stakeholders to explore and implement practical solutions for safer, more sustainable buildings.

New e-SAFE policy papers

Ensuring an integrated and inclusive approach to renovation

Achieving safe, energy-efficient buildings across Europe requires more than just technical upgrades—it demands a people-centered approach. A new e-SAFE policy brief underscores the vital role of co-design in ensuring the success of integrated renovations that address both seismic safety and energy efficiency. The e-SAFE pilot project in Catania is in the spotlight here, showing that collaborative design with residents is key to overcoming barriers and increasing renovation uptake. It ensures tailored solutions to the needs of occupants, improved trust, and lasting community benefits.

Despite the advantages of co-design, regulatory and financial hurdles persist. The brief calls for better integration of funding streams and stronger policy support for participatory approaches. By aligning one-stop shops, renovation passports, and financial incentives with meaningful community engagement, Europe can scale up renovations that are not only technically sound but also socially accepted and locally driven.

Read the policy
brief here

Victoria Taranu, policy officer at BPIE and author of this paper, shares her view on the benefits of co-design, a process which involves key stakeholders such as building occupants and users in the renovation planning.

[Read the interview on BUILD UP here.](#)

Read the policy brief here

Financing for energy and seismic building retrofits

Currently, separate funding streams for energy and seismic renovations hinder cost-effectiveness for integrated solutions. The policy brief highlights how the EPBD recast can help Member States develop financial tools—such as blended public-private investments, energy performance contracts, and revolving funds—to enable holistic retrofits.

It also advocates for aligning financial incentives with policy tools like energy performance certificates, renovation passports, and minimum energy performance standards.

Integrated renovations not only enhance safety and energy efficiency but also improve property value, reduce long-term costs, and support economic and social resilience. This underscores the need for innovative financial models, such as on-bill financing and energy service companies (ESCOs), to lower upfront costs and accelerate market adoption.

Examples of combinations depending on market failures and context

Figure 3: Combining financial instruments for energy renovation. Source: [fi-compass](#).

Save the date: e-SAFE final conference in Brussels

We are excited to announce that the e-SAFE final conference - also known as the 'final clustering event' - will take place on **24 September 2025** in Brussels!

This event marks the final milestone of the project and aims at bringing together experts from across the construction, renovation, and policy sectors to discuss the future of **energy and seismic renovation**.

The conference will gather researchers, construction professionals, building owners, public authorities, and financial institutions to explore innovative solutions, collaboration opportunities, and future strategies for deep renovation, seismic retrofitting, and safety management. A special working session will focus on policy and decision-makers, aiming to build consensus on deep renovation policies and incentives at both the national and European levels.

Stay tuned for more details, including the venue and agenda. This will be a key event to shape the future of building renovation, and we look forward to meeting you there!

e-SAFE stakeholder community

If you'd like to stay abreast on all news related to e-SAFE and seismic renovations in general, we invite you to join our *e-SAFE stakeholder community*.

Join the stakeholders community

Thanks for your attention!

Be sure to **follow us** on **Social Media** to keep upon all the latest **e-SAFE news!**

Partners

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No. 893135.

